

NanoSolveIT

Innovative Nanoinformatics models and tools: towards
a Solid, verified and Integrated Approach to Predictive (eco)Toxicology

Grant Agreement Number 814572

Deliverable Report D1.8

Deliverable	D1.8 Final report on delivered data sets
Work Package:	WP1: NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure
Delivery date:	M56 – 2023-08-30
Lead Beneficiary:	Maastricht University (UM)
Nature of Deliverable:	Report
Dissemination Level:	Public
Licence:	CC-BY 4.0 International

Submitted by:	Egon Willighagen, Ammar Ammar (UM), Tassos Papadiamantis and Iseult Lynch (UoB), Stephen Lofts, Amaia Green Etxabe (UKCEH), Xenia Knigge (BAM), Alexander Lyubartsev (SU), Giusy del Giudice, Laura Saarimäki (UTA)
Revised by:	Xenia Knigge, BAM and Iseult Lynch, UoB
Approved by:	Iseult Lynch, UoB

Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
List of Abbreviations.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
1.2. FAIR-ification solutions.....	5
1.2.1. Bioschemas annotation.....	5
1.2.2. FAIR Maturity Indicators.....	6
1.2.3. eNanoMapper ontology.....	7
1.2.4. European Registry of Materials (ERM) Identifiers.....	7
2. NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure.....	8
2.1. WP1.....	8
2.1.1. RDF Data sets.....	8
2.1.2. NanoSafety Cluster project’s data.....	11
2.2. WP2 data.....	12
2.3. WP3 data.....	21
2.4. WP4 data.....	22
2.5. WP5 data.....	23
2.6. WP6 data.....	24
2.7. Data associated with the NanoSolveIT Cloud.....	25
2.7.1. NanoPharos DB.....	25
2.7.2. Other Cloud Services.....	30
3. FAIR Data and Open Data.....	31
3.1. Open data, unpublished data.....	31
3.2. Propagation of metadata.....	31
3.2.1. Schema.org / Bioschemas.....	31
3.2.1. Zenodo and DataCite.....	32
4. Conclusion.....	35
References.....	36

Executive Summary

This deliverable report provides an overview of data made available by the NanoSolveIT project, either through curation activities on literature data or data generation (experimental or computational) within NanoSolveIT. The report discusses the different ways of making data available: archiving versus interactive access, open licence versus unpublished data, less FAIR versus more FAIR data etc. We also show here that data produced by a project is not only data coming out from experiments funded by that project, but can also include data originating from other projects but curated, integrated, enriched, made more FAIR, or by providing interactive access to it. The latter can mean a custom API to support nanoQSAR modelling approaches, for example. The tables in this deliverable present datasets that NanoSolveIT partners generated, worked on, and/or made available as FAIR or as open data.

It must be stressed that while this is a WP1 deliverable, many NanoSolveIT WPs contributed to this deliverable by releasing datasets in one of the ways as explained in this deliverable.

IMPORTANT: Some of the data is available at this moment only from the NanoSolveIT Google Drive as it is still being validated, annotated and/or prepared for publication and release. Access can be requested via the NanoSolveIT project coordinator. This also applies to private GitHub repositories.

List of Abbreviations

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway; **API** - Application Programming Interface; **ATP** - adenosine triphosphate; **BSA** - Bovine Serum Albumin; **BY** - Attribution (when used as CC-BY); **CC** - Creative Commons; **CNPs** - Carbon nanoparticles; **D** - Deliverable Report (as in D1.2); **DLS** - Dynamic Light Scattering; **DNA** - Deoxyribonucleic acid; **ENMO** - eNanoMapper Ontology; **ERM** - European Registry of Materials; **EU** - European Union; **FAIR** - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable; **GO** - Graphene Oxide; **H2020** - Horizon 2020, the EU research funding programme; **HAXPES** - hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; **HTML** - HyperText Markup Language; **ICP-MS** - Inductively Coupled Plasma - Mass Spectrometry; **ISBN** - International Standard Book Number; **JSON** - JavaScript Object Notation; **JSON-LD** - Linked Data extension of JSON; **kb** - kilobase; **KB** - Knowledge Base; **KE** - Key event; **LDH** - Lactate dehydrogenase; **M** - Milestone (as in M4); **MD** - Molecular dynamics; **MWCNT** - Multi-walled carbon nanotube; **NKI** - NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure; **NM** - Nanomaterial; **NP** - Nanoparticle; **NSDI** - NanoSafety Data Interface; **NSDRA** - NanoSafety Data Reusability Assessment (framework); **OECD** - Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development; **OS** - Operating System; **PBPK** - Physiologically based Pharmacokinetics; **PMA** - phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate; **qPCR** - quantitative polymerase chain reaction; **QSAR** - Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships; **RCF** - Root Concentration Factor; **RDF** - Resource Description Framework; **rGO** - reduced Graphene Oxide; **ROS** - reactive oxygen species; **SEM** - Scanning Electron Microscopy; **SOC** - Surface Oxygen Content; **SPARQL** - Semantic Protocol and RDF Query Language; **TEM** - Transmission Electron Microscopy; **TF** - Translocation Factor; **TG-GATEs** - Open Toxicogenomics Project-Genomics Assisted Toxicity Evaluation System; **UoB** - University of Birmingham; **URI** - Universal Resource Identifier; **URL** - Universal Resource Locator; **UUID** - Universally Unique Identifier; **WP** - Work Package; **XPS** - X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on data used, developed, FAIR-ified or otherwise worked on during the NanoSolveIT project. It will give a perspective on data generated in various work packages, either from wet-lab experiments, from computational modelling workflows or extracted from sources like literature or databases. Figure 1 shows a summarised outline of this work and describes what happened with this data.

Work package 1 (WP1) was tasked with the development of a FAIR knowledge infrastructure, leading to the NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure, reported on in other deliverables. WP1 worked not just on redistributing data sets provided by other WPs, but also on making them reusable. During this project, WP1 partners developed new solutions to support the FAIR-ification of (these) datasets, aiming at making the datasets easier to reuse and more interoperable. For example, we developed a framework based on the FAIR principles but focusing on the needs to actually reuse data in NMs research and risk evaluation. This is explained in more detail in Section 1.2.

Figure 1. The NanoSolveIT data and metadata workflow. The NanoSolveIT data production is complemented with rich metadata, which are then transferred to WP1 for data and metadata management and FAIR-ification. The produced datasets are transferred to the NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure for segmentation and dissemination to the appropriate NanoSolveIT data source for storage, e.g., ready-for-modelling datasets are stored in the NanoPharos database. The NanoSolveIT Knowledge Base and the NanoSolveIT Zenodo Community are linked and publish the respective metadata to external metadata repositories, i.e., Cordis, DataCite, Elixir, Google Dataset Search, RE3Data.org, and the Horizon 2020 project SbD4Nano, for example.

Furthermore, along the lines of the FAIR principles, we wanted to make sure data is findable and accessible. For accessibility, we employed various solutions, allowing us to compare them and to be ready for different kinds of potential use cases. For example, we identified a clear difference in terms of *how* we make data available on how re-used the data is. FAIR and the FAIR community itself focuses a lot on the accessibility of data via archiving of data. The archival process ensures that data remains available for a long time. Zenodo and Figshare, two common archives for research outputs, ensure 20 years or more of access. However, for modelling, searching, and many use cases in nanosafety research, for which we need to have **interactive** access to the data. This need is filled, of course, by “databases” or Knowledge infrastructure.

NanoSolveIT worked on three databases, each with a slightly different focus, but all integrated: 1. the main NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure, 2. a SPARQL endpoint with the WP1 RDF datasets, and 3. the

NanoPharos Database for ready-for-modelling datasets (Section 2.6.1). The SPARQL endpoint data is fully integrated into the NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure, using the FAIR application programming interface (API) provided by SPARQL (see deliverable D1.7 and EU NanoSafety infrastructure partner project NanoCommons deliverable report D7.4). Using a similar approach, the NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure also provides access to two other EU NanoSafety Cluster project datasets, hosted via the NanoSafety Data Interface (see Section 2.1.2).

Finally, various tables in this deliverable report outline the various datasets released, with a name, a short description, and where possible a link. Some datasets are open or already published, while others are not published or otherwise openly released as yet, and then a notice is given that the data is available from the project Google Drive upon request. This list, and the NanoSolveIT Zenodo page, will be further updated as datasets are released for reuse.

1.2. FAIR-ification solutions

As part of the strategy of WP1 around FAIR-ification of NanoSolveIT data, we worked on making metadata more machine readable. The importance of the new nanoinformatics technologies is that metadata (data about data) should be openly shared as much as possible. For example, in the ELIXIR Toxicology Community we worked with the BioSchemas community of the ELIXIR Interoperability platform to make metadata more easily found. The impact of this is that datasets become findable in downstream search engines and indices, including the Google Datasets Search and the “Semantic Landscape” of the H2020 SbD4Nano project. Section 3 will illustrate downstream uses of this metadata. This section introduces some of the ideas to enhance machine readability of metadata developed and/or implemented within NanoSolveIT.

1.2.1. Bioschemas annotation

One way of making metadata describing datasets machine-readable is to provide them in a JSON-LD format, a linked data extension of JSON that can be embedded into web pages (HTML pages), which makes it both an accessible and interoperable resource that is both human- and machine-readable. From this perspective, we used the bioschemas vocabulary, an extension of schema.org vocabulary, to create metadata describing published datasets related to nanosafety expressed in JSON-LD format. Moreover, we created HTML pages describing these datasets where the JSON-LD metadata is embedded into them allowing both humans and machines to read and understand the metadata. This approach has been used in a collaboration with the research infrastructure project [NanoCommons](#) and embedded in the main interactive NanoSolveIT Knowledge Base (see Deliverable report D1.3). Table 1 shows the main elements used to describe datasets using the schema.org and Bioschemas vocabularies.

Table 1: Elements used to describe NanoSolveIT datasets in accordance with schema.org and bioschemas vocabularies.

Metadata Element	Description	Example
identifier	The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of Thing, such as ISBNs, GTIN codes, UUIDs etc. Schema.org provides dedicated properties for representing many of these, either as textual strings or as URL (URI) links. See	10.5281/zenodo.7990302

	background notes for more details.	
name	The name of the item.	Physico-chemical characterization of Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM
description	A description of the item.	Here a dataset of XPS, HAXPES and SEM measurements for the physico-chemical characterization of NPs is presented. The measurements are part of the H2020 project "NanoSolveIT". Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs were provided by Promethean Particles (ERM identifier in the project: ERM00000409)
licence	A licence document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/3.0/de/legalcode
url	URL of the item	https://zenodo.org/record/7990086
keywords	Keywords or tags used to describe some item. Multiple textual entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas, or by repeating the property.	XPS, HAXPES, SEM, nanoparticles, nanosafety, physico-chemical characterization, Fe ₃ O ₄ , ERM00000409 or erm:ERM00000409
creator	The creator/author of this CreativeWork. This is the same as the Author property for CreativeWork	NanoSolveIT
datePublished	Date of first broadcast/publication	2023-05-31

1.2.2. FAIR Maturity Indicators

One of the efforts carried out in WP1 of NanoSolveIT, was to develop a framework to bridge the gap between the datasets produced by wet lab researchers and the needs of the scientific community to enable reuse of this data. The data is usually produced according to a standard (e.g., a minimum reporting standard, a best practice or a community guideline). Both the data and the community standards are mostly not available in machine-readable formats that allow a software to consume them, assess them and integrate them in an automated way. The current data curation practice mostly involves a substantial effort starting with downloading the dataset (or the pdf supplementary file of a publication for example), making sense of the columns, data types, units and outcomes, and then trying to align the reported variables with other datasets (i.e., integrating the data) in order to use it for a new application (e.g., for developing a machine learning) model for NMs risk assessment). One approach to fill this gap, which we implemented in this work, is to convert the available community standards (minimum reporting standards) of the

nanosafety domain into a machine-readable format (namely, JSON-LD) and to make it possible to annotate published datasets with the variables mentioned in the community standards in such a way that computer programs can extract a harmonised set of reported variables from a dataset and assess its completeness or reusability for a specific application. The resulting framework is called NSDRA (NanoSafety Data Reusability Assessment) (<https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2022-l8vk8-v2>) and it is composed of three components:

- 1) twelve minimum reporting standards in the nanosafety domain provided in a machine readable format as FAIR maturity indicators (under sub-principle R1.3),
- 2) a web application to generate machine-readable metadata for published datasets using variables from the minimum reporting standards, and
- 3) a web application (<https://w3id.org/nsdra>) that is able to extract metadata from web pages describing datasets and their measured variables and compare the extracted variables to a minimum reporting standard to assess data completeness and reusability for five applications: Grouping/Read-across, Nanoform Identification, Toxicity Prediction, Regulatory Requirements, and NanoinChI Calculation.

Further details of the NSDRA are provided in Deliverable Reports D1.7 - Initial report on automated data completeness testing and delivered data sets.

1.2.3. eNanoMapper ontology

The eNanoMapper ontology (ENMO) is described in detail in deliverable D1.5, and milestone M4 is the most recent release of the ontology. Here we describe the milestone release of this summer (eNanoMapper 10). A series of minor modifications have been implemented to ensure the ontology's robustness and compatibility. Notably, comprehensive tests have been integrated, encompassing file and dependency integrity checks during file uploads, development tests, and thorough pre-release quality assessments. The complete release notes are available on the [ENMO GitHub repository](#).

Furthermore, the ontology is now listed in and accessible through the [NFDI4Chem Terminology Service](#), an access point for chemistry ontologies developed and maintained by TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology (1–3).

1.2.4. European Registry of Materials (ERM) Identifiers

Multiple datasets for NMs on which NanoSolveIT has done experiments have European Registry of Materials (ERM) Identifiers (4). For example, the “*Physico-chemical characterization of sterilized Co_{1.5}Fe_{1.5}O₄ nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM*” dataset listed before is for the materials with ERM identifiers erm:ERM00000407, erm:ERM00000449, erm:ERM00000428. These identifiers will support the research and data reuse by making sharing and comparing data between labs easier, as well as facilitating searching for other datasets using these specific ERMs via search engines.

Internally, these ERM identifiers have been tracked with a private GitHub repository, available at <https://github.com/NanoSolveIT/nanosolveit-materials>.

2. NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure

This section describes the datasets NanoSolveIT measured or computed, FAIR-ified from external sources, or worked on in other ways. The structure of this section is arranged around the work packages. As much as possible, we refer to other deliverables where readers can find further details.

2.1. WP1

WP1 was about the NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure, but during the project it worked on making not only data from the NanoSolveIT project available, but also made other data available to the project. This is described in the following subsections.

2.1.1. RDF Data sets

A wide range of datasets related to different aspects of NMs research were transformed into RDF and are presented in this section (Table 2). They were obtained from supplementary materials of already published research, annotated with semantic web ontologies, converted into RDF (Resource Description Framework) format and loaded into a SPARQL endpoint to enable querying the data and answering research questions. These datasets offer valuable information for studying various properties and characteristics of NMs, enabling researchers to explore their potential applications, safety considerations, and environmental impacts. These datasets contribute significantly to the field of nanosafety research by providing extensive data on physicochemical properties and cytotoxicity. Researchers can leverage these datasets to enhance their understanding of NM behaviour, support the development of predictive models, and inform the safe design and application of NMs.

In addition to their rich content, an important aspect of these datasets is that they have been converted into RDF format. This conversion plays a pivotal role in making the data more FAIR, which in turn fosters open science and facilitates the discovery and reuse of nano-related datasets by the scientific community. By adopting the RDF format, these datasets gain several benefits. Firstly, RDF provides a standardised and structured approach for representing the data, enabling better organisation and management. It allows researchers to assign unique identifiers to each data point, making them easily findable and citable, thereby promoting attribution and credit to the original authors. Secondly, RDF facilitates accessibility by promoting open data principles: the original data converted into RDF had an open licence; this open licence allowed us to modify the data, i.e., convert it into RDF and make it more FAIR. We inherited the open licence and hosted the data on open platforms like Zenodo, making these datasets freely available to anyone, removing barriers to access and promoting collaboration among researchers. Furthermore, RDF's semantic nature enhances interoperability. Through the use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies, the datasets become linked to established knowledge frameworks, enabling seamless integration with other datasets and fostering interdisciplinary research. This interoperability promotes the discovery of new insights by combining data from multiple sources, ultimately accelerating scientific progress. Lastly, RDF enables reusability by providing a framework for structured and standardised data exchange. It allows researchers to easily extract, integrate, and analyse the data, even across different domains and applications. This reusability aspect is particularly relevant in the field of nanotoxicology, as it allows for the comparison and validation of results, the development of predictive models, and the identification of potential risks associated with NMs. Overall, the conversion of these datasets into RDF format enhances their FAIRness, promoting open science and enabling the scientific community to find, access, interoperate, and reuse nano-related datasets. This not only facilitates knowledge dissemination and collaboration but also fosters data-driven research, leading to a better understanding of nanotoxicity and the development of safer NMs.

Table 2: Datasets related to NMs safety assessment that were transformed into RDF by NanoSolveIT partners

Name	Description	URL
RDF version of supplementary data from the research paper 'Meta-analysis of <i>Daphnia magna</i> nanotoxicity experiments in accordance with test guidelines'	The dataset is an RDF (Resource Description Framework) version of the supplementary data from a meta-analysis conducted by Shin, Hyun Kil and Seo et al. The meta-analysis aimed to investigate the inconsistencies in ecotoxicological assays regarding the risk of nanoparticles (NPs) to <i>Daphnia magna</i> (<i>D. magna</i>), a species of water flea. The dataset includes information from 882 data points obtained from 83 publications, where the physicochemical properties of NPs, experimental conditions of the assays, and measured toxicities to <i>D. magna</i> were extracted. The dataset is divided into different classes based on the state of NPs, and prediction models were developed using a support vector machine for each class. The meta-analyses revealed important factors influencing toxicity, such as the dispersion methods used. The findings suggest that adjustments in dispersion methods for NPs may be necessary in test guidelines to reduce heterogeneity in toxicity assay results. The dataset is available under a CC-BY 4.0 licence and is associated with the NanoSolveIT project.	https://zenodo.org/record/7602354
RDF version of supplementary data from the research paper 'Towards a generalized toxicity prediction model for oxide nanomaterials using integrated data from different sources'	The dataset is an RDF (Resource Description Framework) version of the data from Choi, JS. et al.'s study, which aims to develop a generalised toxicity prediction model for oxide nanomaterials using integrated data from various sources. The dataset consists of 41 materials and includes information on material characteristics, assay types, cell lines, species, and toxicity measurements. There are a total of 59 assays, 90 measurement groups, and 1239 endpoints in the dataset. It covers seven types of nanomaterials, nine assay types, 11 endpoint types, and seven units of measurement. The dataset is available under a CC-BY 4.0 licence and is associated with the NanoSolveIT project.	https://zenodo.org/record/5743204
RDF version of supplementary data from the research paper 'Predicting Cytotoxicity of Metal	The dataset is an RDF version of the data from the research paper titled "Predicting Cytotoxicity of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles Using Isalos Analytics Platform" by Papadiamantis et al. The RDF data is associated with the NanoSolveIT	https://zenodo.org/record/5743788

<p>Oxide Nanoparticles Using Isalos Analytics Platform”</p>	<p>project and was published on Zenodo. The dataset includes various features related to metal oxide NPs and their cytotoxicity. The features include material type, core size, hydrodynamic size, surface charge, surface area, assay details, cell information, exposure time, exposure dose, and various other parameters related to the NMs. The dataset includes 14 different NM types, such as CuO, ZnO, and Mn₂O₃, with information on their core size, hydrodynamic size, surface charge, surface area, and other properties. There are also 23 different assays, including ATP, Viability, and Ec (cytotoxicity) assays. Each row in the dataset represents a different metal oxide NP sample with its associated properties and cytotoxicity measured in terms of viability.</p>	
<p>RDF version of supplementary data from the research paper ‘Manually curated transcriptomics data collection for toxicogenomic assessment of engineered nanomaterials’</p>	<p>The dataset titled "RDF version of the data from Saarimaki et al. Manually curated transcriptomics data collection for toxicogenomic assessment of engineered nanomaterials (2020)" provides a curated collection of transcriptomics data for toxicogenomic assessment of engineered NMs. The dataset was created as part of the NanoSolveIT project and is available under the CC-BY 4.0 licence. It includes various features such as experiment metadata and differential gene expression data. The experiment metadata includes information on treatments, groups, organisms, biological systems, doses, time points, slides, arrays, dyes, platforms, and filenames. The differential gene expression data contains features such as log fold change, average expression, t-statistic, p-values, adjusted p-values, and gene IDs. The dataset includes information on 22 material types, 35 assays, 440 measurement groups, 249,350 endpoints, 22 nanomaterial types, 35 assay types, 3 endpoint types, 21 units, 3 species (Mus musculus, Homo sapiens, Rattus norvegicus), 39,947 unique genes, 22,841 unique human genes (ENSG), 16,450 unique mouse genes (ENSMUSG), 609 unique rat genes (ENSRNOG), and 47 not annotated genes.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/5744003</p>
<p>RDF version of supplementary data</p>	<p>The dataset "RDF version of the data from Papadiamantis. et al. Computational enrichment</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/5744082</p>

<p>from the research paper “Computational enrichment of physicochemical data for the development of a zeta-potential read-across predictive model with Isalos Analytics Platform”</p>	<p>of physicochemical data for the development of a zeta-potential read-across predictive model with Isalos Analytics Platform. NanoImpact (2021)" offers enriched physicochemical data for the development of a zeta-potential read-across predictive model. It includes information on various features such as metal core, coating, type of coating, ageing, diameter, shape group, geometric surface area, corresponding sphere diameter, zeta potential, and others. The dataset was created as part of the NanoSolveIT project, published on Zenodo and is available under the CC-BY 4.0 licence. The dataset reports on 69 materials and provides measurements for 3 assays with a total of 207 measurement groups and 1518 endpoints. Moreover, it covers 14 different NM types and 23 endpoint types.</p>	
<p>RDF version of supplementary data from the research paper “Meta-Analysis of Nanoparticle Cytotoxicity via Data-Mining the Literature”</p>	<p>The dataset "RDF version of the data from . Labouta et al. Meta-Analysis of Nanoparticle Cytotoxicity via Data-Mining the Literature. NanoImpact (2019)" offers a large collection of data obtained from a meta-analysis of nanoparticle cytotoxicity through data mining the literature. It includes information on various features such as NM type, organic or inorganic nature, coating, diameter, dose, zeta potential, cell line, cell line or primary designation, human or animal origin, animal species, cell morphology, cell age (embryonic or adult), cell organ or tissue, exposure time, test assay, test indicator, biochemical metric, and cell viability. The dataset was created as part of the NanoSolveIT project, published on Zenodo and is available under the CC-BY 4.0 licence. The dataset includes information on 118 different materials and provides measurements for 267 assays. With a total of 354 measurement groups and 6061 endpoints, it offers a wealth of data for studying nanoparticle cytotoxicity. The dataset covers 33 different nanomaterial types, 3 assay types, 3 endpoint types, and 8 different species.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/5744302</p>

2.1.2. NanoSafety Cluster project’s data

The NanoSolveIT Knowledge Base (NSIT KB) has an API integration with the NanoSafety Data Interface (NSDI) and our NSIT KB provides access via this integration within seconds. Details are provided in deliverable D1.2 (“Knowledge Infrastructure API”) and D1.3 (“Maintenance and Evaluation”). As one specific aspect, the data integrated directly into the NKI is organised around NMs rather than datasets, i.e., each

integrated data, whether physico-chemical characterisation, toxicology or ecotoxicology, always primarily refers to the NM measured rather than a specific dataset. This organisation is meant to simplify data reuse by integrating information available for a given NM. Table 3 summarises previous EU-funded projects whose datasets have been made available via the NSIT KB.

Table 3: Datasets related to NMs that have been integrated into the NanoSolveIT Knowledge INfrastructure from previous EU-funded projects

Name	Description	URL
NanoFase	Data from the NanoFase project. This data is integrated directly into the NKI.	www.nanotoxkb.eu
NanoMILE	Data from the NanoMILE project. This data is integrated directly into the NKI.	
eNanoMapper	Data from the eNanoMapper FP7 project. This data is integrated via API integration with the Nanosafety Data Interface.	
NANoREG	Data from the NANoREG project. This data is integrated via API integration with the Nanosafety Data Interface.	
RDF datasets	RDF based datasets provided as SPARQL endpoints described in Section 2.1.1 are integrated via API with the NanoSafety Data Interface.	

2.2. WP2 data

Here we describe data from NanoSolveIT WP2. WP2 was the main web-lab or experimental data generation WP, with a focus on gap-filling experiments to supplement datasets from previous projects, and bespoke data generation to support model development and/or validation. Experimental work consisted of synthesis and characterisation of NMs (see deliverable D2.2 for details), toxicity testing of the NMs using a range of approaches (see deliverable D2.3 for details), and ecotoxicity testing using a range of aquatic and terrestrial species (see deliverable D2.4 for details). Some data has been published already, for example on Zenodo, while other datasets are at this moment only available via the NanoSolveIT Google Drive. Table 4 summarises the datasets that resulted from the activities in WP2.

Table 4: Datasets generated in WP2 covering NMs characterisation, toxicity and ecotoxicity assessment

Name	Description	URL
Ecotoxicity: impacts of eight nanomaterials on reproduction of <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (<i>C. elegans</i>)	Acute toxicity (96h reproduction, offspring count) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH

Ecotoxicity: impacts of eight nanomaterials on growth of <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Acute toxicity (4, 24, 48, 72, 96h growth, body length) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: impacts of nanomaterials on reactive oxygen species (ROS) production in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Acute toxicity (4, 24, 48, 72, 96h ROS production, H2DCFDA assay) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: genotoxicity of nanomaterials to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Acute toxicity (4, 24, 48, 72, 96h relative lesion frequency per 10 kb DNA, qPCR) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: impact of nanomaterials on <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> gene expression	Acute toxicity (4, 24, 96h expression of 16 genes (average Ct)) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: impact of nanomaterials on <i>Pseudomonas putida</i> growth rate by optical density	Toxicity (18 time points up to t=16h 43min, growth by optical density measurement) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Pseudomonas putida</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: impact of nanomaterials on <i>Pseudomonas putida</i> growth rate by colony count	Toxicity (16h, growth by colony count) of freshly dispersed NMs to <i>Pseudomonas putida</i> .	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UKCEH
Ecotoxicity: Acute (48h) toxicity of panel of fresh versus aged Ag and TiO ₂ NMs to <i>Daphnia magna</i>	Using the OECD 202 acute immobilisation test, a panel of 11 NMs (Ag and TiO ₂ NMs with different coatings) were evaluated in 3 test media (HH Combo and Class I and Class V representative river waters) immediately following dispersion and following ageing for 2 years in medium. NM characterisation at both time points includes DLS (Size, Zeta potential), TEM images. Data published in Varsou et al., 2021 (5).	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zul?datasetID=5
Ecotoxicity: Chronic reproductive toxicity over multiple generations of panel of fresh versus aged Ag and TiO ₂ NMs to	Using the OECD 211 chronic (reproduction) test, a panel of 11 NMs (Ag and TiO ₂ NMs with different coatings) were evaluated in 3 test media (HH Combo and Class I and Class V representative river waters)	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UoB Daphnia

<p><i>Daphnia magna</i> (OECD 211)</p>	<p>immediately following dispersion and following ageing for 6 months in medium. Data on life stage including growth and reproduction data in FO (parental generation) and then paired continuous exposure and recovery generations (F1-F3). NM characterisation at both time points includes DLS (Size, Zeta potential), TEM images, accompanied by ICP-MS data on metal loading in daphnids at selected timepoints. Data is published in Ellis et al., 2020 and Ellis et al., 2021 (6,7).</p>	
<p>Ecotoxicity: Acquired protein corona on Ag and TiO₂ NMs during chronic exposure to <i>Daphnia magna</i> (OECD 211)</p>	<p>Using the OECD 211 chronic (reproduction) test, a panel of Ag NMs with different coatings) were evaluated in 3 test media (HH Combo and Class I and Class V representative river waters) immediately following dispersion and following ageing for 6 months in medium. At day 7 of exposure, particles were recovered from the test medium and their protein corona determined using liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). ICP-MS analysis of Ag content in the daphnids was performed to correlate dose-response in terms of signalling pathways perturbed by the NMs exposure. Data is published in Ellis et al., 2020 (8).</p>	<p>NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UoB Daphnia</p>
<p>Ecotoxicity: Mechanistic exploration of impacts of GO and CeO₂ NMs on the freshwater planarian <i>Dugesia japonica</i></p>	<p>Dataset of mechanism of effect of GO and CeO₂ NMs on growth and regeneration (amputated) of <i>Dugesia japonica</i> worms, using a 48-h acute toxicity test, respectively. End-points assessed include stem cell proliferation and differentiation, cell apoptosis, generation of ROS and oxidative DNA damage during planarian regeneration, impacts on energy metabolism, mitochondrial membrane integrity, and neuron regeneration. Data published in Xie et al., 2022 and Xie et al, 2023 (9,10).</p>	<p>NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UoB Planaria</p>
<p>Ecotoxicity: Assessment of the antibacterial activity of GO and rGO NMs to gram positive and gram negative</p>	<p>Antibacterial performance series of GO and rGO materials with different SOC towards <i>Escherichia coli</i> (<i>E. coli</i>, Gram-negative) and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (<i>S. aureus</i>, Gram-positive) by evaluating the total cell</p>	<p>NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP2 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files UoB Bacteria GO</p>

<p>bacteria: effect of Surface Oxygen Content (SOC)</p>	<p>growth, biofilm formation as well as oxidative stress in two representative media (without/with proteins). Physical interactions with bacteria were assessed by SEM and a liposome leakage assay. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations explored NMs–lipid membrane interaction. Published in Gao et al., 2023 (11).</p>	
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $\text{Co}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$\text{Co}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by partner University of Birmingham (UoB). ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000407, ERM00000449, ERM00000428. The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with bovine serum albumin (BSA), microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940271</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $\text{Co}_{2.25}\text{Fe}_{0.75}\text{O}_4$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$\text{Co}_{2.25}\text{Fe}_{0.75}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000406, ERM00000448, ERM00000427). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940538</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterile ZnO NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>Sterile ZnO nanoparticles were synthesised under aseptic conditions at Mintek, South Africa (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000584) and characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990213</p>

	survey and high-resolution spectra of the sample.	
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised AIOOH NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	AIOOH nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000396, ERM00000438, ERM00000417). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966245
Physico-chemical characterization of sterile citrated stabilised Au NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	Sterile citrated stabilised Au nanoparticles were synthesised under aseptic conditions at Mintek, South Africa (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000582) and characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of the sample.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990250
Physico-chemical characterization of sterile Fe ₃ O ₄ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	Sterile Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles were synthesised under aseptic conditions at Mintek, South Africa (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000583) and characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of the sample.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990301
Physico-chemical characterization of Fe ₃ O ₄ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles. (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000409). The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990085
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised TiO ₂ PVP NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	TiO ₂ PVP NPs were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966354

	<p>and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000414, ERM00000456, ERM00000435). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised ZnO NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>ZnO nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000416, ERM00000458, ERM00000437). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940162</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000399). The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7986672</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised CeO_2 NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>CeO_2 nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000398, ERM00000440, ERM00000419). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941461</p>

<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised Fe₂O₃ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>Fe₂O₃ NPs were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000410, ERM00000452, ERM00000431). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941001</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised TiO₂ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>TiO₂ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000413, ERM00000455, ERM00000434). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941566</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised ZrO₂ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>ZrO₂ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000404, ERM00000446, ERM00000425). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7965536</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of CeO₂/Co₃O₄ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>CeO₂/Co₃O₄ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000397). The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7989698</p>

	survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised Co_3O_4 NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	Co_3O_4 nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000405, ERM00000447, ERM00000426). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941248
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised TiO_2 D540 NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	TiO_2 D540 nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000415, ERM00000457, ERM00000436). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7961317
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $\text{Co}_{0.75}\text{Fe}_{2.25}\text{O}_4$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM	$\text{Co}_{0.75}\text{Fe}_{2.25}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000408, ERM00000450, ERM00000429). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940769
Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $\text{Ce}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$	$\text{Ce}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7965445

<p>NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000401, ERM00000443, ERM00000422). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $Ce_{0.75}Zr_{0.25}O_2$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$Ce_{0.75}Zr_{0.25}O_2$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000400, ERM00000442, ERM00000421). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966133</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $Ce_{0.25}Zr_{0.75}O_2$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$Ce_{0.25}Zr_{0.75}O_2$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB (ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000402, ERM00000444, ERM00000423). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966165</p>
<p>Physico-chemical characterization of sterilised $Ce_{0.1}Zr_{0.9}O_2$ NMs by XPS / HAXPES / SEM</p>	<p>$Ce_{0.1}Zr_{0.9}O_2$ nanoparticles were characterised by XPS, HAXPES and SEM to determine the physico-chemical properties. The particles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated by different sterilisation methods by UoB</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7965602</p>

	(ERM-Identifier in the project: ERM00000403, ERM00000445, ERM00000424). The treatment finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. The dataset includes SEM images, XPS and HAXPES survey and high-resolution spectra of all the samples.	
--	---	--

2.3. WP3 data

WP3 activities involved curation and integration of existing transcriptomics datasets, as well as bespoke validation activities to support specific hypotheses. Table 5 summarises the datasets that resulted from the activities in WP3.

Table 5: Datasets curated or generated in WP3 covering toxicogenomics and multi-omics analysis of NMs impacts on cells and animals

Name	Description	URL
Multi-omics analysis of dynamic dose-response in macrophages recapitulates multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT)-induced lung fibrosis	PMA-differentiated THP-1 cells were exposed to Mitsui-7 MWCNTs with varying concentrations (5, 10 and 20 ug/ml) for 24, 48 or 72 hours. Gene expression and DNA methylation changes were evaluated by microarrays.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE146710
Manually curated transcriptomics data collection for toxicogenomic assessment of engineered nanomaterials	Transcriptomics data derived from NMs exposures in human, mouse and rat (<i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i>) were curated, preprocessed and analysed. Accompanying physico-chemical properties of the materials were also collected and reported. The final collection comprises 101 entries with preprocessed expression matrices (microarrays) or count matrices (RNA seq) as well as results of differential expression analysis.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6425445
A Curated Gene and Biological System Annotation of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) Related to Human Health	A collection annotated AOPs, with KEs annotated to established gene sets (gene ontology terms, pathways, etc.). The repository provides KE-gene associations as well as biological system annotations for the AOPs.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980953
Data & code repository for the article "An ancestral molecular	This repository contains the relevant data and code supporting the study "An ancestral molecular response to nanomaterial	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7674574

response to nanomaterial particulates"	particulates"(12). In detail the following data sources have been included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the preprocessed transcriptomic datasets GSE157266 and GSE148705 included in the discovery set (curated_transcriptomic_data.zip); - supplementary materials of the paper, including curated molecular descriptors panels and the NM gene signature (supplementary_files.zip); - The preprocessed microarray transcriptomics data for drug exposure curated from a selection of the Open Toxicogenomics Project-Genomics Assisted Toxicity Evaluation System (TG-GATEs) data (transcriptomic_data_drug_exposures.zip); - the chemical signatures collected from the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD) (CTD_signatures.zip); - the list of dose dependent genes for individual transcriptomic dataset (dose_dependent_genes.zip); - the relevant code and input data (code.zip and input_data.zip) 	
--	--	--

2.4. WP4 data

WP4 activities involved physics-based 1st principles calculations of properties associated with NMs interactions with biomolecules including amino acids, proteins and lipids. Datasets generated in WP4 include adsorption free energies of a range of NMs, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Datasets generated in WP4 include computational calculations of biomolecule binding to NMs

Name	Description	URL
Adsorption free energies of biomolecular fragments to NMs	Adsorption free energies and associated potentials of mean force of 32 biomolecular fragments representing amino acids, fragments of lipids and sugars, to 30 NM surfaces including metal oxides (TiO ₂ , ZnO, SiO ₂ , Fe ₂ O ₃), quantum dots (ZnS, CdSe), carbon-based (graphene, CNTs, amorphous C) and some functionalized / coated forms, computed in atomistic molecular dynamics / metadynamics simulations	https://zenodo.org/record/8297848

2.5. WP5 data

WP5 activities involved curation and integration of datasets relating to NMs physico-chemical characteristics and toxicity, as well as generation of computational predictions of NMs physico-chemical properties and toxicity utilising machine learning approaches including Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSARs). Table 7 summarises the datasets that resulted from the activities in WP5.

Table 7: Datasets curated or generated from WP5 computational activities

Name	Description	URL
Photodegradation of phenol (TOH) by TiO ₂ -based nanophotocatalysts determined in line with the SAPNet methodology	The independent variable (predictor) is the intensity of photoluminescence at 398 nm and with use of a logistic regression model connects the ability of photocatalytic degradation of phenol (endpoint) with this experimentally derived property.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297022
Predictive nano-QSAR modelling of the cytotoxicity using epithelial cells obtained from Chinese hamster ovary (CHO-K1 cell line) for hybrid TiO ₂ -based nanomaterials	Results obtained from the developed model indicated that the cytotoxicity of hybrid TiO ₂ -based NMs is related to additive electronegativity (χ_{mix}) of studied NMs that are indirectly related to the electron generation and ROS formation. ROS production is the most common cause of NMs toxicity in the literature .	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297048
The influence of the properties of inorganic solvents on the hydrodynamic diameter of TiO ₂ NMs	In this model the property of a NM is predicted not on the basis of descriptors characterising the chemical composition of NMs or physical properties of the initial nanoforms, but on the basis of descriptors describing the dispersion medium (pH, ionisation potential (IP), D3_HeteroNonMetals) and the property of NMs dependent on it (zeta potential (ζ)).	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297068
Identification of factors determining the process of aggregation / agglomeration of metal oxide NMs in a biological medium	The model allows to identify factors determining the process of aggregation / agglomeration of metal oxide NMs in a biological medium and to verify the importance of ion adsorption and protein adsorption in this process. Model confirms the significant effect of protein adsorption on the hydrodynamic diameter of metal oxide particles in the biological medium, and does not confirm the significant effect of ion adsorption in this process. It's an example of modelling the properties of NMs, where	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297079

	apart from the descriptors describing the structure of nanoparticles, there are also parameters characterising the medium.	
Influence of protein corona on cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles against human keratinocyte cell line (HaCaT)	The model identified, among the factors determining the cytotoxic properties of metal oxide nanoparticles against HaCaT cell lines, a number of variables related to the processes occurring on the surface of nanoparticles in a biological medium, including the ability to form protein corona.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297121
Curated dataset on protein's properties and post-translational modification protein properties	This dataset presents curated information regarding PTM-related changes in the physicochemical properties of the 16 most abundant plasma proteins, i.e., Serum Albumin, Serotransferrin, Antithrombin-III, Apolipoprotein A-I, Apolipoprotein A-IV, Apolipoprotein B-100, Apolipoprotein C-II, Apolipoprotein C-III, Apolipoprotein E, Clusterin, Complement C3, Haptoglobin, Histidine-rich glycoprotein, Mannose-binding protein C, Haemoglobin, and Fibrinogen alpha chain.	https://zenodo.org/record/8314626

2.6. WP6 data

WP6 activities involved curation and integration of datasets related to occupational and environmental exposure to NMs, datasets regarding biodistribution of NMs, and datasets for deep learning models, as well as literature curated datasets relating to NMs interactions with plants. Table 8 summarises the datasets that resulted from the activities in WP6.

Table 8: Datasets curated for or generated by WP6 computational activities

Name	Description	URL
Occupational exposure dataset for TiO ₂ , carbon black and TiO ₂ and Ag;X	Experimental size distributions (Gaussian distribution) of particles vs emission rates to be used as input for the occupational exposure (13).	https://zenodo.org/record/8321185
Images of daphnids (control and exposed to NMs) over multiple generations, scored by experts as toxic or non-toxic and resulting deepDaph predictions	Microscopic images of <i>Daphnia magna</i> show malformations such as altered tail lengths and changes in overall size. These images also reveal uncommon lipid concentrations and unusual shapes of lipid deposits, which are attributable to either direct exposure or parental exposure to engineered NMs.	https://zenodo.org/record/8321246

Dataset underpinning the development of a PBK model for inhalation of TiO ₂ NPs in rats	This dataset contains data extracted from the publication of Kreyling et al. (2019) regarding a 2-hour inhalation experiment in rats, with tissue and excreta samples taken over a period of 28 days post exposure.	https://zenodo.org/record/8322777
Plant model: Literature dataset enriched with atomistic NMs physico-chemical descriptors for prediction of plant uptake and translocation	A literature dataset (Wang et al., 2021 https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c01603) which included plant uptake and translocation of NMs extracted from peer-reviewed publications from 2011-2021, consisting of 400 datasets for hydroponic and 300 datasets for soil studies, with calculated values for root concentration factor (RCF) and translocation (TF) were calculated based on the concentrations of NM elements in plant roots, shoots, and media. The dataset was enriched with computational nanodescriptors (atomistic and periodic-table based) and used to develop a machine learning model to predict RCF and TF for NMs not included in the dataset used to train the model. A publication and web-application for the model are being finalised currently.	NanoSolveIT Google Drive: WP6 > Deliverables > raw data for the deliverables > Data files for Plant Uptake 10.5281/zenodo.8322276 (reserved DOI)

2.7. Data associated with the NanoSolveIT Cloud

The NanoSolveIT cloud platform is described in detail in another deliverable (D7.4). Because several of the services integrated into the Cloud Platform have a relation to datasets too and the data is not reported earlier, we want to report on that here too. For example, several services provide interactive access to data, like the SPARQL endpoint with chemical-protein binding data, the AOP-Wiki Data, and the data loaded into the NanoPharos database. Some of this data is used by us, but not redistributed by us. For example, the AOP-Wiki RDF is created and distributed by project partners; however, the ChEMBL RDF was originally developed by project partners, but further maintenance and extension has long been taken over by the ChEMBL team itself. For the purpose of FAIR, we found it helpful to provide the relevant data citations here.

2.7.1. NanoPharos DB

NanoPharos (<https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zul>) is a database dedicated to computational data that is ready-to-use for modelling purposes, co-developed with NanoSolveIT. More specifically, the database enables the development of nanoQSAR, read-across and other types of predictive models by giving access to NMs properties, their biointeractions and adverse effects, thus it greatly contributes to the *in silico* assessment of NMs toxicity and evaluation of NM functionalities. Another aspect of the NanoPharos database is the support of the already developed models within NanoCommons and NanoSolveIT projects. These models are supported with the necessary documentation regarding the methods that were applied to develop the models, define their domain of applicability and validate their performance. In this framework,

the data used to build the models are hosted in the NanoPharos database to ensure their long-term accessibility and further increase stakeholders' confidence when using the models or in case that confirming reproducibility of the results through re-creation of the models is desirable. The NanoPharos database is in fact a means to achieve FAIR analysis of NMs data with transparent and open approaches through all modelling aspects. The datasets already included in the database are briefly presented below in Table 9.

Table 9: Ready for modelling datasets available through the NanoPharos database

Name	Description	URL
Cytotoxicity data for 14 metal oxide NMs	Curated dataset (retrieved from S2Nano database - data produced in: doi.org/10.1021/nn3010087) containing 14 distinct metal oxide (MexOy) nanoparticles (NPs), including 15 physicochemical, structural and assay-related descriptors and 62 atomistic computational descriptors (in total 494 data points - Licence: CC-BY 4.0.) and exploited to produce a robust and validated <i>in silico</i> model for prediction of NP cytotoxicity using Isalos Analytics Platform. More information about the data can be found in Ref. (14). Access the model through NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform: https://cellviability.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zuI?datasetID=1
A collection of 34 curated transcriptomics datasets for toxicogenomic assessment of 12 engineered NMs	A collection of human, mouse and rat toxicogenomics datasets for 12 engineered nanomaterials extracted from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) and the ArrayExpress databases and manually curated by Saarimäki <i>et al.</i> , 2021. More information about the data can be found in Ref. (15). Licence: CC-BY 4.0.	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zuI?datasetID=2
Zeta potential dataset for 69 engineered NMs	Curated dataset (raw data produced by the FP7 project NanoMILE (16)) containing 69 distinct engineered nanomaterials (ENMs), including 21 physicochemical, structural and computational descriptors. This dataset (Licence: CC-BY 4.0.) is exploited to produce a ζ -potential read-across predictive model using Isalos Analytics Platform (More information about the data can be found in Ref. (17)). Access the model through NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform: https://mszeta.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zuI?datasetID=3
Solubility data of C60 fullerene in 124	Curated dataset (Licence: CC-BY 4.0.) containing 124 distinct solvents and solubility	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zuI?datasetID=4

solvents	data (expressed in terms of logarithmic values of molar fractions that correspond to the Gibbs free energy changes in the solvation process) of C60 fullerene including 5 computational molecular descriptors. The data are ready for QSAR modelling applications. More information about this dataset can be found in Ref. (18).	!datasetID=4
Acute ecotoxicity (<i>Daphnia Magna</i>) dataset of 11 NMs	Ecotoxicity data (353 data points/11 NMs - Licence: CC-BY 4.0.) curated for nanoinformatics modelling including information regarding acute toxicity to <i>Daphnia Magna</i> of freshly dispersed versus medium-aged NMs and physicochemical descriptors, and exploited to produce read-across predictive models using Isalos Analytics Platform (More information about the data can be found in Ref. (5)). Access the relevant model through NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform: https://ecotox.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu!datasetID=5
Metal oxide toxicity dataset utilising theoretical and experimental descriptors	Cytotoxicity data in three different cell lines of 26 metal oxide NM facets in replicates of varied experimental settings including 32 descriptors (physicochemical, molecular, image analysis and periodic table descriptors - Licence: CC-BY 4.0.). Data are curated and used for the development of nanoQSAR models. More information about the data can be found in Ref. (19). Access the relevant model through NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform: https://facetcytotoxicity.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu!datasetID=6
Computational data for the toxicity and bioactivity assessment of 83 functionalized MWCNTs	A library of 83 surface-modified MWCNTs, with an identical core of a controlled size distribution is included in this dataset as presented by Zhou <i>et al.</i> , 2008 (20). Since the surface modification differentiates the MWCNTs, each sample is represented by its ligands. Mold2 software included in KNIME through Enalos+ nodes was used in order to calculate 777 descriptors that encode two-dimensional chemical structure information of the ligands (Licence: CC-BY 4.0.). For each MWCNT sample toxicity and biological activity (protein binding of carbonic anhydrase) data are included. More	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu!datasetID=7

	<p>information about the data can be found in Ref. (21). Access the relevant model through: http://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/CNT/</p>	
Cell membrane damage assessment of 42 metal oxide NMs	<p>Cell membrane damage assessment data obtained from <i>in vitro</i> test systems of two different metal oxide nanoparticles (24 titanium dioxides and 18 zinc oxides). The experimental data consist of different combinations of physicochemical properties and the corresponding biological endpoint values (damage to cellular membranes as measured by Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release). Reference (22) (Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)</p>	<p>https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=8</p>
Toxicity data of 30 copper NMs against <i>Escherichia coli</i>	<p>A dataset including the pH, temperature, aeration rate, concentration of NMs and concentration of bacteria on the toxicity of zero valent copper nanoparticles against <i>Escherichia coli</i> collected using a centroid mixture design of experiment. (Reference (23), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)</p>	<p>https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=9</p>
Surface adsorption dataset of 28 probe compounds	<p>This dataset contains the surface adsorption properties of a 40 nm diameter MWCNT, coated with hydroxyl derivatives. Five nanodescriptors representing the surface adsorption interactions of the MWCNT with biological components are included. A set of 28 compounds with diverse physicochemical properties are used as probe compounds for predicting the adsorption coefficient (k) of this particular MWCNT. The adsorption coefficients converted to the logarithmic scale are also included in the dataset. (Reference (24), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)</p>	<p>https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=10</p>
Periodic table-based data for the cytotoxicity assessment of 17 metal oxide NMs	<p>Cytotoxicity data of seventeen metal oxide nanoparticles to bacteria <i>Escherichia Coli</i> expressed as the negative logarithm of concentration for 50% effect. Seven periodic table descriptors are included, obtained from the molecular formula of the NMs' core. (Reference (25), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)</p>	<p>https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=11</p>
Photo-induced cytotoxicity of 17 metal oxide NMs to <i>Escherichia coli</i>	<p>A dataset of photo-induced toxicity of 17 metal oxide NM to <i>Escherichia coli</i>. The toxicity is expressed in terms of the logarithmic values of LC50 (the concentration</p>	<p>https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=12</p>

	of the NMs that proved to be fatal to 50% of the bacterium) and it is measured after exposure to natural sunlight irradiation and to dark conditions. (Reference (26), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)	
Cytotoxic effects in <i>Escherichia coli</i> of 16 metal oxide NMs	A collection of 26 physicochemical properties and the cytotoxicity against <i>Escherichia coli</i> of 16 metal oxide nanoparticles. The cytotoxicity is expressed as the effective concentration of a compound that brings about a 50% reduction in bacteria viability, EC50. This dataset is exploited to produce QSAR-type predictive models for the prediction of the metal oxide NMs effects. (References (27,28), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=13
Cytotoxicity dataset of 25 metal (hydr)oxide NMs	A collection of 25 metal oxide and metal hydroxide engineered NMs with different particle dimensions and shapes (spheres or rods). In total 12 descriptors are included in this dataset belonging to two categories: dimensional (nano) and composition-related (non-nano) descriptors. The toxicity data of the 25 NMs on the murine cell line RAW 264.7 are included (LDH release, TNF- α production and ROS production) in this dataset. In addition, an LDH score cut-off value of 1.5 is settled on to categorise NMs as “cytotoxic” (LDH score above 1.5) or “non-cytotoxic/safe” (LDH score below 1.5). (Reference (29), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=14
Interaction energies between 17 carbon nanoparticles and the SARS-CoV-2 RNA fragment	A set of physicochemical and molecular descriptors for 17 different types of carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) including fullerenes, single-walled and MWCNTs, and graphene. The total potential energies, the “van der Waals” energies, and the electrostatic energies between the CNPs and a SARS-CoV-2 RNA fragment are also available. (Reference (30), Licence: CC-BY 4.0.)	https://db.nanopharos.eu/Queries/Datasets.zu/?datasetID=15

2.7.2. Other Cloud Services

Finally, we summarise other data sources that have been integrated into the NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform, as briefly presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Other data sources integrated into the NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform

Name	Description	URL
Adverse Outcome Pathway Wiki RDF	This dataset is the RDF generated from the AOP-Wiki data release (aopwiki.org/downloads). It was generated using a Jupyter notebook that is available on GitHub (github.com/marvinm2/AOPWikiRDF), and the process and additional description of the RDF have been published (31).	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297026
ChEMBL: protein binding info and assay data	ChEMBL is a manually curated database of bioactive molecules with drug-like properties. It brings together chemical, bioactivity and genomic data to aid the translation of genomic information into effective new drugs (32).	https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/chembl/ChEMBL-RDF/31.0/
BridgeDb	BridgeDb is a framework to map identifiers between various biological databases. These mappings are provided for genes, proteins, genetic variants, metabolites, and metabolic reactions.	https://data.bridgedb.org/
Molecular Pathway database access with SPARQL queries	The service contains a SPARQL endpoint that is loaded with RDF of the WikiPathways database (https://wikipathways.org/ , (33,34)), and is updated each month. On top of that, a SNORQL User Interface facilitates the exploration of data and provides example queries. WikiPathways is a molecular pathway database to capture molecular descriptors, interactions and processes, and allows data analyses. This includes the Nanomaterials Portal (nanomaterials.wikipathways.org/).	https://wikipathways-data.wmcloud.org/ and GPML pathways files are archived on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/wikipathways/

3. FAIR Data and Open Data

3.1. Open data, unpublished data

NanoSolveIT is not always the source of the data presented in this deliverable, reflecting the Open Science progress of the EU NanoSafety Cluster and the field in general: we have been able to reuse data from other projects. Secondly, not all data made more FAIR had an open data licence to begin with: that means that while we can reuse such data, redistribution is a lot more complicated. Moreover, some data will be part of a pending publication and is currently not publicly available as yet. The status and licence of the data is made available in many cases as machine readable metadata.

However, a lot of data has already been made available, either as archived data on Zenodo, as interactive data, or both.

But an open licence alone is not a sufficient requirement for reuse. Our WP1 work on the FAIR maturity indicators reviewed what domain-specific requirements need to be met in order to facilitate and increase the likelihood of data reuse. Moreover, we found that different kinds of reuse have different requirements. The framework allows users of the NanoSolveIT platform to evaluate which datasets, from this project or other projects, meets their needs.

3.2. Propagation of metadata

Here we reflect on what open data we leave for adoption by other projects. Figure 1 showed the overview of the full NanoSolveIT Knowledge Infrastructure. It highlights how data and metadata propagates via the infrastructure and WP1, illustrates that the NKI is a platform to share the data and the metadata, and WP1 makes what data is passed along more FAIR. Part of that effort is ensuring that we communicate the data and the metadata in a more FAIR manner than we received it.

This section highlights one aspect of this FAIR-ification process, which is a common aspect of all datasets: the metadata. This typically includes an identifier, a name, a short description, ideally with some information about the authors/creators, release date, etc. This metadata is important provenance that supports the process of future researchers deciding which datasets they want to use. The wide dissemination of this metadata supports the findability aspect of FAIR of these datasets.

3.2.1. Schema.org / Bioschemas

To ensure metadata findability for the NanoSolveIT datasets, we collaborated with other projects on the topic of sharing metadata. For example, we worked with ELIXIR Europe to make toxicology research more available. Partners contributed to the effort of the new ELIXIR Toxicology Community and the tasks they started some time ago. This includes working with the Bioschemas team that develops (life sciences) extensions to the schema.org project of the major search engines (Google, Bing, etc). Continuing an earlier effort, we joined NanoCommons in a project to list Open-licensed and archived data sets (nanocommons.github.io/datasets/) and made sure that NanoSolveIT datasets were listed too (see Figures 2 and 3).

datasets

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7088624

Overview of open datasets released by NanoSafety Cluster projects

This list provides an overview of archived datasets with an open license. Each one of them can be cited with [DataCite](#) and various datasets are not only downloaded from the archives but can also be interactively explored via databases.

Additional datasets and databases that provide interactive access to these datasets can be reported [here](#).

Physico-chemical characterization of sterile Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM

- Date: 2023-05-31
- License: [Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial 3.0 Germany](#)
- Project: [NanoSolveIT](#)
- URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/7990302>
- DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7990302

Physico-chemical characterization of sterile citrated stabilized Au nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM

- Date: 2023-05-31
- License: [Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial 3.0 Germany](#)
- Project: [NanoSolveIT](#)
- URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/7990251>
- DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7990251

Physico-chemical characterization of sterile ZnO

Figure 2: Screenshot of the NanoCommons 'Overview of open datasets' page, showing two of the open-licensed, archived datasets. This page has besides the human oriented HTML page visualised here, also [schema.org JSON-LD](#) annotation embedded in the document, that is picked up by the search engines. This ensures that, for example, [Google Dataset Search](#) will know these datasets and return them in search results when people search for keywords.

3.2.1. Zenodo and DataCite

A second community standard to support communication of metadata is DataCite, a standard specifically aimed at citing data as simple as citing a journal article (35, 36). This too greatly supports making data more findable, and therefore boosts the FAIR-ness of the data. DataCite currently does not index Bioschemas annotation, but it does index everything archived on Zenodo (see Figure 4). This is why archiving data on Zenodo, when ready, is part of our Data Management Plan. Tables 3-9 above provide DOIs for multiple NanoSolveIT datasets archived on Zenodo. Of course, these are picked up by DataCite, but when linked to the grant, also automatically become visible in the CORDIS database.

Google

Saved data sets

1 dataset found

Physico-chemical characterization of Fe₃O₄...
nanocommons.github.io
Updated May 31, 2023

Explore at: nanocommons.github.io

311 scholarly articles cite this dataset ([View in Google Scholar](#))

Unique identifier
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990086>

Data set updated
May 31, 2023

Dataset authored and provided by
NanoSolveIT

Licence
[Attribution-NonCommercial 3.0 \(CC BY-NC 3.0\)](#)
Licence information was derived automatically

Description
Here a dataset of XPS, HAXPES and SEM measurements for the physico-chemical characterization of nanoparticles is presented. The measurements are part of the H2020 project "NanoSolveIT". Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were provided by Promethean Particles (EMR identifier in the project: ERM00000409).

Not seeing a result that you expected?
[Learn](#) how you can add new data sets to our index.

Figure 3: Searching for the ERM identifier ERM00000409 finds one of the NanoSolveIT datasets annotated with schema.org annotation that mentions the identifier. This search result is made findable via the NanoCommons list of open datasets.

2 Works

Creators & Contributors ?

- Knigge, Xenia 2
- Radnik, Jörg 2

Publication Year

- 2023 2

Work Type

- Dataset 2

License

Registration Agency

- DataCite 2

Physico-chemical characterization of sterilized ZnO nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM

Xenia Knigge & Jörg Radnik

Content published 2023 in [Zenodo](#)

Here a dataset of XPS, HAXPES and SEM measurements for the physico-chemical characterization of sterilized nanoparticles is presented. The measurements are part of the H2020 project "NanoSolveIT". ZnO nanoparticles were provided by Promethean Particles and treated differently by project partners from the University of Birmingham (EMR-Identifiers in the project: ERM00000416, ERM00000458, ERM00000437). The particles were treated by different sterilization methods (autoclave or microwave) and BSA was or was not added as stabilizer. This finally leads to five different samples: pristine, autoclave, microwave, autoclave with BSA, microwave with BSA. Prior to the measurements, the samples were prepared from the solution as drop cast on Si wafers. First SEM and EDS measurements were performed, followed by XPS and HAXPES measurements on the same samples. Here at first survey spectra were recorded followed by high resolution spectra. For XPS / HAXPES several Si-wafers were mounted together on one platen. The platen was left in the intro chamber of the instrument for several hours before the measurement started. Equipment: SEM images were acquired with a *Supra 40* (Zeiss) SEM equipped with a *Quantax 400* (Bruker) SDD EDS spectrometer. For X-ray spectroscopy experiments, a combined XPS / HAXPES spectrometer (*Quantax* from ULVAC-PHI) was used, where XPS is measured at 1486.6 eV (monochromatic Al K α source) and HAXPES at 5414.9 eV (monochromatic Cr K α source). Here it is possible to perform the measurements at the exact same position. Data: For SEM, the data are given in .tif format. For XPS / HAXPES the raw data are given as .spe (PHI format) and .npl (VAMAS format) files. The measurement conditions are given in the data files. Naming of data: SEM: *sample_treatment (n)*, with n a consecutive number. XPS / HAXPES: For the .spe files *Pn.m.o.sample_treatment* and for the corresponding .npl files: *m.npl* with Pn: platen-number, m: spectrum number (order of the measurements); o: point-number, of the position on the sample, sample_treatment with "m" for microwave and "a" for autoclave. The authors thank Sigrid Benemann, who performed the SEM measurements.

DOI registered May 16, 2023 via DataCite.

[Dataset](#)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940162>

Figure 4: Searching for ERM identifier ERM00000416 finds a NanoSolveIT dataset archived in Zenodo using the DataCite search engine.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable has given an overview of data made available by the NanoSolveIT project. It discusses the different ways of making data available: archiving versus interactive access, open licence versus unpublished data, less FAIR versus more FAIR data etc.

We also show here that the data produced by a project is not only data coming out from experiments funded by that project (be they experimental or computational), but can also include data originating from other projects but integrated, made more FAIR, or by providing interactive access to it. The latter can mean a custom API to support nanoQSAR modelling approaches, for example. The tables in this deliverable present datasets we worked on and made available as FAIR or as Open data. Clear licencing information accompanies all datasets as part of their metadata.

References

1. Strömert P, Hunold J, Castro A, Neumann S, Koepler O. Ontologies4Chem: the landscape of ontologies in chemistry. *Pure Appl Chem* [Internet]. 2022 Mar 24 [cited 2022 Jul 23];0(0). Available from: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/pac-2021-2007/html>
2. Herres-Pawlis S, Koepler O, Steinbeck C. NFDI4Chem: Shaping a Digital and Cultural Change in Chemistry. *Angew Chem Int Ed* [Internet]. 2019 Jul 17 [cited 2019 Jul 24]; Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/anie.201907260>
3. Steinbeck C, Koepler O, Bach F, Herres-Pawlis S, Jung N, Liermann J, et al. NFDI4Chem - Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Chemistry in Germany. *Res Ideas Outcomes*. 2020 Jun 26;6:e55852.
4. van Rijn J, Afantitis A, Culha M, Dusinska M, Exner TE, Jeliaskova N, et al. European Registry of Materials: global, unique identifiers for (undisclosed) nanomaterials. *J Cheminformatics*. 2022 Aug 24;14(1):57.
5. Varsou DD, Ellis LJA, Afantitis A, Melagraki G, Lynch I. Ecotoxicological read-across models for predicting acute toxicity of freshly dispersed versus medium-aged NMs to *Daphnia magna*. *Chemosphere*. 2021 Dec;285:131452.
6. Ellis LJA, Kissane S, Hoffman E, Valsami-Jones E, Brown JB, Colbourne JK, et al. Multigenerational Exposure to Nano-TiO₂ Induces Ageing as a Stress Response Mitigated by Environmental Interactions. *Adv NanoBiomed Res*. 2021 Jun;1(6):2000083.
7. Ellis LA, Kissane S, Hoffman E, Brown JB, Valsami-Jones E, Colbourne J, et al. Multigenerational Exposures of *Daphnia Magna* to Pristine and Aged Silver Nanoparticles: Epigenetic Changes and Phenotypical Ageing Related Effects. *Small*. 2020 May;16(21):2000301.
8. Ellis LJA, Lynch I. Mechanistic insights into toxicity pathways induced by nanomaterials in *Daphnia magna* from analysis of the composition of the acquired protein corona. *Environ Sci Nano*. 2020;7(11):3343–59.
9. Xie C, Li X, Hei L, Chen Y, Dong Y, Zhang S, et al. Toxicity of ceria nanoparticles to the regeneration of freshwater planarian *Dugesia japonica*: The role of biotransformation. *Sci Total Environ*. 2023 Jan;857:159590.
10. Xie C, Li X, Guo Z, Dong Y, Zhang S, Li A, et al. Graphene oxide disruption of homeostasis and regeneration processes in freshwater planarian *Dugesia japonica* via intracellular redox deviation and apoptosis. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2023 Jan;249:114431.
11. Guo Z, Zhang P, Xie C, Voyiatzis E, Faserl K, Chetwynd AJ, et al. Defining the Surface Oxygen Threshold That Switches the Interaction Mode of Graphene Oxide with Bacteria. *ACS Nano*. 2023 Apr 11;17(7):6350–61.
12. Del Giudice G, Serra A, Saarimäki LA, Kotsis K, Rouse I, Colibaba SA, et al. An ancestral molecular response to nanomaterial particulates. *Nat Nanotechnol*. 2023 Aug;18(8):957–66.
13. Tsiros P, Cheimarios N, Tsoumanis A, Jensen ACØ, Melagraki G, Lynch I, et al. Towards an *in silico* integrated approach for testing and assessment of nanomaterials: from predicted indoor air concentrations to lung dose and biodistribution. *Environ Sci Nano*. 2022;9(4):1282–97.
14. Papadiamantis AG, Jänes J, Voyiatzis E, Sikk L, Burk J, Burk P, et al. Predicting Cytotoxicity of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles Using Isalos Analytics Platform. *Nanomaterials*. 2020 Oct 13;10(10):2017.
15. Saarimäki LA, Federico A, Lynch I, Papadiamantis AG, Tsoumanis A, Melagraki G, et al. Manually curated transcriptomics data collection for toxicogenomic assessment of engineered nanomaterials. *Sci Data*. 2021 Feb 8;8(1):49.
16. Joossens E, Macko P, Palosaari T, Gerloff K, Ojea-Jiménez I, Gilliland D, et al. A high throughput imaging database of toxicological effects of nanomaterials tested on HepaRG cells. *Sci Data*. 2019 May 2;6(1):46.
17. Papadiamantis AG, Afantitis A, Tsoumanis A, Valsami-Jones E, Lynch I, Melagraki G. Computational enrichment of physicochemical data for the development of a ζ-potential read-across predictive model

- with Isalos Analytics Platform. *NanoImpact*. 2021 Apr;22:100308.
18. Gharagheizi F, Alamdari RF. A Molecular-Based Model for Prediction of Solubility of C₆₀ Fullerene in Various Solvents. *Fuller Nanotub Carbon Nanostructures*. 2008 Jan;16(1):40–57.
 19. Thwala MM, Afantitis A, Papadiamantis AG, Tsoumanis A, Melagraki G, Dlamini LN, et al. Using the Isalos platform to develop a (Q)SAR model that predicts metal oxide toxicity utilizing facet-based electronic, image analysis-based, and periodic table derived properties as descriptors. *Struct Chem*. 2022 Apr;33(2):527–38.
 20. Zhou H, Mu Q, Gao N, Liu A, Xing Y, Gao S, et al. A Nano-Combinatorial Library Strategy for the Discovery of Nanotubes with Reduced Protein-Binding, Cytotoxicity, and Immune Response. *Nano Lett*. 2008 Mar 1;8(3):859–65.
 21. Varsou DD, Afantitis A, Tsoumanis A, Melagraki G, Sarimveis H, Valsami-Jones E, et al. A safe-by-design tool for functionalised nanomaterials through the Enalos Nanoinformatics Cloud platform. *Nanoscale Adv*. 2019;1(2):706–18.
 22. Sayes C, Ivanov I. Comparative Study of Predictive Computational Models for Nanoparticle-Induced Cytotoxicity: Comparative Study of Predictive Computational Models. *Risk Anal*. 2010 Nov;30(11):1723–34.
 23. Rispoli F, Angelov A, Badia D, Kumar A, Seal S, Shah V. Understanding the toxicity of aggregated zero valent copper nanoparticles against *Escherichia coli*. *J Hazard Mater*. 2010 Aug 15;180(1–3):212–6.
 24. Xia XR, Monteiro-Riviere NA, Mathur S, Song X, Xiao L, Oldenberg SJ, et al. Mapping the Surface Adsorption Forces of Nanomaterials in Biological Systems. *ACS Nano*. 2011 Nov;5(11):9074–81.
 25. Kar S, Gajewicz A, Puzyn T, Roy K, Leszczynski J. Periodic table-based descriptors to encode cytotoxicity profile of metal oxide nanoparticles: A mechanistic QSTR approach. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2014 Sep;107:162–9.
 26. Pathakoti K, Huang MJ, Watts JD, He X, Hwang HM. Using experimental data of *Escherichia coli* to develop a QSAR model for predicting the photo-induced cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles. *J Photochem Photobiol B*. 2014 Jan;130:234–40.
 27. Puzyn T, Rasulev B, Gajewicz A, Hu X, Dasari TP, Michalkova A, et al. Using nano-QSAR to predict the cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles. *Nat Nano*. 2011 Mar;6(3):175–8.
 28. Mu Y, Wu F, Zhao Q, Ji R, Qie Y, Zhou Y, et al. Predicting toxic potencies of metal oxide nanoparticles by means of nano-QSARs. *Nanotoxicology*. 2016 Oct 20;10(9):1207–14.
 29. Forest V, Hocheplied JF, Leclerc L, Trouvé A, Abdelkebir K, Sarry G, et al. Towards an alternative to nano-QSAR for nanoparticle toxicity ranking in case of small datasets. *J Nanoparticle Res*. 2019 May;21(5):95.
 30. Zhang F, Wang Z, Vijver MG, Peijnenburg WJGM. Probing nano-QSAR to assess the interactions between carbon nanoparticles and a SARS-CoV-2 RNA fragment. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2021 Aug;219:112357.
 31. Martens M, Evelo CT, Willighagen EL. Providing Adverse Outcome Pathways from the AOP-Wiki in a Semantic Web Format to Increase Usability and Accessibility of the Content. *Appl Vitro Toxicol*. 2022 Mar 17;avt.2021.0010.
 32. Willighagen EL, Waagmeester A, Spjuth O, Ansell P, Williams AJ, Tkachenko V, et al. The ChEMBL database as linked open data. *J Cheminformatics*. 2013;5(1):23.
 33. Martens M, Ammar A, Riutta A, Waagmeester A, Slenter DN, Hanspers K, et al. WikiPathways: connecting communities. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2021 Jan 8;49(D1):D613–21.
 34. Martens M, Verbruggen T, Nymark P, Grafström R, Burgoon LD, Aladjov H, et al. Introducing WikiPathways as a Data-Source to Support Adverse Outcome Pathways for Regulatory Risk Assessment of Chemicals and Nanomaterials. *Front Genet*. 2018 Dec 21;9:661.
 35. Brase J. DataCite - A Global Registration Agency for Research Data. In: 2009 Fourth International Conference on Cooperation and Promotion of Information Resources in Science and Technology [Internet]. Beijing, China: IEEE; 2009 [cited 2020 Feb 28]. p. 257–61. Available from: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5361881/>

36. Neumann J, Brase J. DataCite and DOI names for research data. *J Comput Aided Mol Des.* 2014;28(10):1035–41.